

DIPLOMACY AND WAR: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF US-IRAN CONFLICT

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Abstract

Examining the US and Iran conflict with historical background till current situation by adopting the mixed methodology analysis case study approach. How the conflicted rooted in Israel because it is actual a US and Israel foreign policy. Role of Diplomates here's it discussed in the case of US-Isreal and Iran conflict. Negotiations possible in war time or in normal situations shows the mediator countries relations with others states, here like Pakistan's relations with US and Iran attracted both for trust. Iran is an oldest Islamic country of the world and become more prominent by their 1979 revolution. Israel become the Jewish State by the UNO Partition plan to resolve the issue between Arabs and Jewish people in 1948 but it changed the whole situation. We will discuss the major issues on both sides in the dispute which are the basis of the conflict. Proxies, IRGC to direct invasion. How the negotiators tried but failed to reach a deal or how the Islamabad talks were unable to reach a comprehensive deal. Role of Pakistan's Prime Minister and CDF Asim Minur in Islamabad Talks. How make the situations worst the assassinations of Iranian's and destruction in Iran and Iranian attacks on Isreal and gulf countries. Blockade of Straint of Hurmoz. Foreign policies of countries how affecting the whole scenario because of Iran foreign policy against US-Isreal and US-Isreal foreign policy against Islamic Iran. America is known for economy and power in the world and have the hegemonic style. In this paper it will be explain the entire background of the conflict, efforts for conflict resolution and temporary ceasefire, peace settlements between USA and Iran. Iran assets, sanctions on Iran and no nuclear deal are the major challenges and on the other hand US-Isreal policies for not reaching deal or peace settlements and it's still a continuous situation.

INTRODUCTION

Wars ends and peace come always with the diplomacy. Diplomacy is the vital force which used by the diplomates and leaders of the nations in the entire world for negotiations, conflicts resolutions and peace creation. Diplomacy has protracted history. After World War one diplomates gain more significance in the world because due to globalization. All those Countries whom got independence after World War one and after end of colonialism are still facing many issues like

territorial borders, economy, and poverty. To resolve all the issues around the world countries needs diplomacy and the great minds of diplomates. Iran, Israel and America war or dispute effecting whole the world economy especially the Middle East countries because of American Airbases or alliances. In 1948 philistine was divided and Israel become the independent state by the UN Partition plan but the Arabs was rejected this decision and become a disputed land

from that day. Israel secured the 78% of the land while west bank and Gaza were under the Joden and Egypt control. Rise of the Jewish population in the philistine by time ultimately increased the Arabs opposition. Situations become more and more critical by the time and become more threatening after 1979 when resolution in Iran took place. Iran become the huge supporter of the Muslim world and always tried to support Muslims of the entire world. Israel is a Zionist state and try to build a massive monopoly on the world especially on the Palestine for the Jewish people and America always support Israel.

LITERATURE REVIEW

US and Israel attacked on Iran on 28 February 2026 and resume the war in the region. During attacks Iranian Supreme Leader Ali Khamaiani and other reputable officials were killed in response of these attacks Iran started launching missile and drones' series against all the allies of the USA in the Middle East because of failed negotiations said Global witness. Assassination of 175 school children's make situation worst. Omani mediators said just one night before the USA attacks that Iran will not become nuclear power, Trump said it just because of Iranian nuclear program and now it has been obliterated. These hostiles will never end quickly it is real risk may continue in the region.

After the World War 2 the rivalries in the Middle East despite the regional ties and non-state actors in the region confirmed that the nature of dynamics of war is now transformed. Arabs are not directly involved in war but its grounds are Arab-Israel conflicts relating to Israel-Palestine issue and Israeli efforts to gain control of whole Palestine territory described by Syed Fraz Hussain Naqvi. More actors make situation more unsatisfying and complex in the region, makes worst the neighborhoods.

Political leader of Hamas Ismail Hania and Hassan Nasrullah were killed in during 2024 Israeli attacks in Iranian territory and in Beirut respectively. In retaliation, Iran attacked on Israel in October 2024. It is classifying as International Armed Conflict. These acts are in exchange according to the common article 2 (Lieber

Institute, Nov 24) continuous attacks from both sides represents the same conflict and crucial for Iran and Israel. One thing is more important that this confrontation is continuous since long time and how long the conflict not the short period. General closure of military operations with supports international humanitarian law with the aim to end hostilities. In case Iran-Israel hostilities and continuous attacks but no other military operations are involved like troops mobilizations in foreign countries. Currently no chance of closures of military operations but ICTY provided the whole assessment how end of armed conflicts. Non-recognition of Israel by Iran precludes the possibility of ceasefire between two states. Situation on both sides Iran and Israel explicit the threat of wars again in the region and will be a challenge of IHL. Since first Israel Airstrikes in 2018 shows that Iran-Israel is in direct confrontation for last more than 7 years. According to the situation if both Iran-Israel are not ready for the treaty then can be considered as the in-war situation like Syria and Israel are consider in situation of war after 1967 war between them in terms of international law.

Israel direct confrontation changed it to a direct open hostile now it is not the proxy war and ends deterrence. It begins in April 2024 when Israel Attacks on Iranian consulate. It has been explained by Abdul Wasi and others in paper Iran Israel conflicts 2024-25 by using realistic theory approaches. War produced chaos due to alliances between gulf countries and United States, Russia and China involvement in the region. Direct missiles hitting from the both Iran and Israel continuously escalating security concerns and Israelis attacks on Iranian nuclear program. Direct assassinations of Iranian Leaders and military officers by attacking them creates turbulence conditions in the country. State and non-state actor's boundaries are ambiguous in the Iran-Israel rivalry in the geopolitical landscapes. How Teheran, Hezbollah, Zaynabiyoun, Fatemiyoun and IRGC operating strikes respond against Israeli attacks is their foreign policy and revolutionary agenda. How they are operating in the entire region demonstrates their power and security are their core objectives. This historical trajectory

rooted on 1979 revolution and initiated anti-Zionist and anti-western ideology in their foreign policy and it is particularly related with Ayatullah Khomeini. Ayatullah Khamenei Supreme Leader of Iran describes during 2000 to 2015 Israel as cancer and needs to remove. Iran drives his foreign policy on grounds of Islamic revolution and deters amines exceptionally Israel. Iran established proxies in Iraq, Syria and Lebanon.

USA become peer with Israel on Iran War in February 2026 and joined Israel air operations. Iran response was also extensive launch drones and missiles to stop air operations in the gulf countries also blocked Strait of Hormuz. Donald Trump aim was regime change. Iran no attacked directly to US, US-Israel attacks are not justified by International Law (Article 2(4) UN Charter) use of forces is justified just for self-defense. US Claims that Iran will have nuclear weapons has no hefty evidence. (2 March 26, Susan M. Akram and others). Attacks like US-Israel requires UN authorization according to the R2P re-commitment collective action charter. Killing school children's and other civilians are not legitimate in international humanitarian law.

Conflict between Iran and Isreal is turbulent Middles East have impacts on the geographical, political and economy of the whole region. In past US President Windrow Wilson support self-determination and US president harry Truman pressurize diplomatically Soviet Union for removal of force from Iran. Good terms changed into rivalry during the cold war and after revolution in Iran. US Imposed sanctions on Iran to weaken ability but with the help of proxies in Iraq, Yemin, Libya and Lebanon Iran impacts US interests in the region particularly in Saoudi Arabia. After renunciation nuclear deal of US and Iran in 2018 Iran seized ships and attacked on infrastructure in Gulf countries in mid of 2019 (Simon Tanios). Trump and Netanyahu make the path more difficult to a peace settlement by killing the diplomatic people of Iran by attacks and they were don't have the diplomatic mindset leaders anymore. Iran was in closteroviral situation but they can't want to stop till the permanent solution. Iran needs collation but have no time for negotiations or coalitions, because of Trump

strategy of genocides. Trump war is in Netanyahu favor but it is the Trump idiosyncrasy not the Netanyahu pressure. Trump doing beyond the limits just for personal interest for national interest. US also has no technical or professional team for negotiations and realists deals not support diplomacy. US misunderstandings about Iran seeing like US is entangled in the war. US claims for the Uranium looks baseless because Iran has 300kg of it and 1200kg requires to make a bomb.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this article the researcher has adopted Mixed methodology comparative case study approach along with descriptive, historical and analytical research techniques to analyzes the war dynamics and diplomacy. Methodology in common is the study of research methods. The term can also refer to the method's philosophical discussion of associated background assumptions. Qualitative method will describe the whole scenario till end. Quantitate methods will used to gather the numerical data. This normally involves various steps, like choosing a sample, collection of data from the sample, and interpreting the data.

It involves deep study of diplomatic process and escalation. All the conditions of diplomacy and war and vice versa. How it shapes the political outcomes and role of sanctions in escalation and de-escalation.

Researcher adopts Descriptive, Historical and analytical techniques for research aims to accurately, clearly and systematically describe situation or phenomenon. It is useful when not much is known yet about the topic or problem. Before you can research why something happens, you need to understand how, when and where it happens.

Researcher adopts Historical research is a process of collecting and interpreting data about past events or ideas in order to find how they affected the present events and ideas. It studies possible reasons behind certain events to explain their influence on the events that followed.

Analytical research is a specific type of research that involves skills like critical thinking and the evaluation of facts and information relative to the

research being conducted. A variety of people including students, doctors and psychologists use analytical research during studies to find the most relevant information.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What was the diplomatic efforts of stakeholders during the war?
2. Why peace is obligatory between USA-Israel and Iran?
3. Role of Pakistani Leaders and Officials in Ceasefire?

MAIN ARGUMENT

Mediation is the tools for peace settlements and conflict resolution in all over the world. Countries always design their foreign policy in their national interest. Iran and US-Israel have the long conflict background. In the history of Iran and Israel we

have seen too many incidents between Iran and Isreal after the Islamic revolution in Iran. Base of conflict is the UN partition plan of Israel and Palestine because after Islamic revolution aims of Iranian foreign policy completely changed. Iran did not recognize Israel as state. From the day of partition Israel tried to build monopoly in the whole region tried for dominance. In November 1979 US imposed sanctions on Iran when 66 Americans including diplomates were hostage by Irani students. In 1980 Iran and Israel indirectly negotiate clandestinely and Isreal provided military support to Iran during Iran-Iraq war but cooperation comes to end in 1990s. In June 1982, 2nd Israel invasion of Lebanon, Iran trained Hezbollah but Hezbollah officially aligned with Iran in 1985.

Irani Revolution Father, Ruhollah-Khomeini

On 15 March 1995 and 6 May 1995 US President Bil Clinton imposed sanctions on Iran and banned Investments and trades with Iran. “Between” 1990 to 2000 most of the sanctions imposed on Iran changed the relations with other

countries. It is the history of the world when sanctions-imposed countries relations become more complex and sanctions increase the distance, which not only weakens the ties between the countries, but also creates a deadlock that closes

all avenues for dialogue which also creates great difficulties in the countries' efforts to improve themselves as we see the same in the Versailles case.

In 2002 Iran-Israel conflict escalated due to Iran direct involvement in weapons supply to Palestinian and stealthy nuclear program with the assistance of Russian engineers. In 2003 UN Security council resolution-imposed sanctions on Iran and banded on nuclear-related technology and freeze assets of all the companies related the nuclear enrichment program.

In July 2006 Lebanon commence war by Hezbollah, Iran supported with IRGC and provided long range missiles (C-802 Anti-ship missile, Zelzal-2 missile) also monitor the entire period. Following the situations Isreal threaten Irani nuclear program will be crushed but Iran

escalate support for Hamas and Palestinian Islamic Jihad (Summar Reins operation). In 2006 Israel alleged Iran to fiancé bombing in Tel Aviv in response of British and American forces operations in Iraq. 2006 war clarify that Iran fighting with proxies in the region against Israel. Iran and US don't address the direct diplomatic relations in the history but in 2009 first time in Switzerland significant conversation about the nuclear program was take up by the Irani and US diplomates in Geniva but no successful deal become possible and, in the result, harsh sanctions were imposed on Iran. In 2010 USA and Israel crushed Iranian uranium enrichment program, Iranian nuclear program is exceptional threat for Israel. Sanctions, War threats and regional conflicts are not in number between Iran and other countries of the region but US-Israel are in exceptional because US and Israel foreign policy.

Iranian diplomat Saeed Jalili and US negotiator William Burns held the highest-level direct talks between the two countries in 30 years.

5 years period (2010-2015) considered as Shadow War because of nuclear scientist's assassinations, Cyber-attacks, Tit-for-tat operation and Syrian convey attacks. After 2010 Iranian nuclear program was the primary target. In 2012, National authorization act and Iran threat reduction and Syrian Humans Rights act was passed and US imposed sanctions on Ira and Syria. On 14 July

2015 Iran publicizes comprehensive nuclear agreement (Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action) with world powers which limits the uranium enrichment in exchange of uplifting of economic sanctions. In 2018 US president Donald J. Trump withdraw from the agreement and imposed sanctions again after the Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu statement that's proclaimed

he has evidence that Iran has sufficient uranium for nuclear program. European countries tried to maintain the agreement by battering but during 2020 to 2023 Iran increased nuclear activities and reached closure to the nuclear weapons by suspending IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency) monitoring. UN, Australia and USA imposed sanctions on Iran multiple time giving different reasons and sanctions always shut doors of negotiations. When tried to crush by someone it makes the situation more complex and close the doors for the diplomatic negotiations. During the whole period of almost 47 years (1979-2026) both countries Iran and Israel did not success in making a deal to end the wars in the region. Wars between Iran-Israel and with proxies creates unrest in the entire region even the USA ally countries Saudia Arabia, UAE, Qatar, Kuwait, Oman and Bahrein dose reach any type of deal which prevents wars in the future and its massive negligence of diplomatic ties and relations.

By the time, tensions between Iran and Isreal become worst. Challenges in the region converted proxies' wars into direct invasion. On 10 May 2018 Israel launched (Operation House of Cards) and started massive strikes on Iran. Israel demolished Iranian infrastructure in Syria and tried to prevent Iranian military presence in Syria. Simultaneously Israel increased intervention in Gaza. US plays very particular role in the Iran-Israel conflict. In 2020, the US drone attack on the orders of Donald Trump killed Qasem Soleimani, an Iranian general belonging to the IRGC, which further aggravated the situation and further enhanced the role of the Iranians in the region, adding another new wave to their role-playing, which made the situation in the region completely ready for war. 11 April 2021 Iran alleged Israel attacks on nuclear facility in Natanz but Israeli government denied. All the events of the past make these tensions between west and Iran become more harmful effecting the whole region particularly gulf countries.

Drone attack, Escalation of tensions in Lebanon and Syria, Hamas attack on Israel, Houthai attacks, Gaza attacks, assassination of Razi Mousavi and October 2023 Regional Spillover all these activities from both sides between Iran and Isreal escalated tensions and provided grounds for direct invasion. In 2023 UN Security Council lifted the sanctions relates to ballistic missiles and others. There is no evidence of any attempt by either side to establish diplomatic relations, which is why it can be said that when any country in the world abandons the path of diplomacy and opts for war, the result is only destruction, loss of human lives, and economic crisis. We can definitely conclude that wars only bring destruction, but diplomacy opens the doors for peace and high-quality, sustainable relations, which the world requires at this time.

Isreal attack on multiple Iranian gas pipeline and "Shadow War" with proxies converted into direct invasion when they opt the direct confrontations in 2024 situation become worst. Israel Bombed direct on Iranian consulate in Syria Damasus in response Iran launched missiles in Damasus on Israel forces but Israel intercepted most of them with US support. On 19 April 2024 Israel attacked on airport in Isfahan. When Israel assassinated Hamas leader Isma'il Haniyeh, Secretary General of Hezbollah Hassan Nasrullah, it acted quickly and pushed the region into a full-scale war by launching operation "New Order". No negotiators were found in this situation and no diplomatic events was conducted from both sides. IRGC took over the charge of Portugal registered ships in Strait of Hormuz and Israel request to EU to impose sanctions on Iran. In results EU expand sanctions and prohibited all type of Martials used in manufacturing of missiles and sanctions targeted the Iran Shipping lines. These all-repeating actions and attacks from both sides provided base for stronger reactions retaliations to both countries and pull the entire region in the war and also provide grounds to subsequent 2025 and 2026 regional wars.

Israeli building destroyed during Irani attacks

12 days war between Iran and Israel began when Israel attacked Iran nuclear facilities in month of June 2025 it was an open armed conflict makes the situation more annoying. US-Israel claimed Iran is near to be a nuclear power and it will be a threath for the western countries because of his Islamic ideology and Iran foreign policy prohibited to recognize Israel as an independent state and still don't accept the UN partition plan for Israel and Palestine. Israel assassinates political leaders, high military officials and civilians and hit drones on public places, hospitals and nuclear sites. Iran retaliated by hitting 500 missiles and 1000 suicide drones. Israel destroyed air defense system when Iran retaliates and attacked on US military base in Qatar (Al Udeid air base), firstly US intercepted Iranian missiles then bombed on Iran three nuclear facilities in Iran. More the 1000 casualties were reported in Iran during attacks. US provided air defense support to Israel after that Israel and

Iran were ready for the ceasefire on US pressure but US brooked ceasefire firstly. On 24th June 2025 ceasefire agreement was reached to final and both countries decided for no more escalation announced by Donlad J. Trump US President by surprising the world. Firstly, Iranian medica said it is fabrication but after few hours Abbas Argchi Iranian foreign minister if Isreal stop escalation, then Iran will also stop it. US president Trump posted on X "The ceasefire is now in effect. Please do not violate it". Trumps demanded Unconditional surrender from Iran and floated the controversial idea of regime change in Iran. Isreal and Iran both decided no more escalation and Trump said both come to me for ceasefire. Qatar saved the Iranian ceasefire agreement. Iran stated that it as "imposition of a ceasefire on the Zionist enemy" and Isreal stated that it is "a great success." It was the end of war in general but not was the conflict resolution.

Iran building destroyed in US-Israel air attacks

Iran Supreme Leader Ayatollah Khamenei who was killed in first attacks on 28 Feb 2026

In this paper, we have described the background of the entire conflict in a complete and comprehensive brief, in which we have briefly reviewed all the events that took place from 1979 to 2025, in which we have told you how diplomacy failed, how activities continued on both sides, how different countries continued to participate in it, how different sanctions imposed on Iran that blocked all avenues of diplomacy, and how America continued to participate in this war. But this situation changed completely in the year 2026 and a new situation arose that was much different and more serious than before. US-Israel both involved in genocides and attacks compel Iran for the war. War took on a different and more serious situation because it had now become a full-scale war because the United States had joined it with a new goal, the main goal of which was to bring about regime change in Iran and, along with regime change, to completely prevent Iran from becoming a nuclear power so that Iran could never become a nuclear power. On 28 February 2026 USA and Israel launch a new wave of missiles on Iran and during the first wave Irani Supreme Leader Ali Khamenei was killed which converted the war into an extreme large-scale armed conflict. Donald J. Trump given the name to this operation "Epic Fury" and now directly involved in invasion on Iran. This operation changed the directions of the war. US attacked on Minab School in Hormozgan province in Iran and killed more than 175 children's and it was a war crime. More than 1000 civilians were killed in attacks by Israel-US

airstrikes. US-Israel bombing on multiple locations like hospitals, infrastructure and particularly on historical places destroyed much in Iran. Assassination of Ali Larejani Secretary of supreme national council of Iran was a huge loss for Iran and for the whole situation because Ali Larejani was playing most important in foreign policy of Iran. In retaliation Iran started attacks on Israel and all the US airbases in the entire region. Retaliation creates chaos in the entire region and make the situation more challenging. Iran attacked on US military base in Kuwait, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Oman, Cyprus and Bahrain. More than 15 US soldiers were killed in the region and more than 400 wounded. US officials who were posted in the region was used the civilized hotels and places to live but most of them return back to US by the order of govt. Iran also launched missiles and drones on different areas of Israel firstly attacked on Tal'Aviv on 28 February 2026. Iran used cluster bombs on Israel and two civilians were killed, IRGC said it is for the revenge of blood of Ali Larejani and his companions. US-Israel target was regime change and Iran and destroy the Iran nuclear program. After the assassination of Ali Khamenei his son Mujtaba Khamenei become the 3rd supreme leader of Iran who joined IRGC in 1987 and served during Iran-Iraq war. Israel also attacked in Lebanon and Iraq, more than 2000 civilians were killed in Lebanon. Behind all this situation are US President Donald Trump and Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu, who believe that

Iran is a dangerous state for Western countries, especially Israel, and also behind all this war is America's foreign policy, which is to prevent Iran

from becoming a nuclear power, as well as the plan for a Greater Israel.

Both Pictures shows Minab School situated in Hormozang Province of Iran which was destroyed in 1st US-Israel attack

Players of the War, Sequence is left to right, Binjamin Netanyahu Israeli Prime Minister Mujtaba Khamenei Supreme Leader of Iran and Donald J. Trum US President.

All these activities changed the map of the entire region and soon the entire region was engulfed in war, in which the United States, Iran and Israel

emerged as major characters, but along with them, many countries, that is, the entire region, were engulfed and the situation in the entire region

became very serious. Not only did the war engulf this region, but its effects were seen all over the world. A wave of inflation swept through countries all over the world, the biggest reason for this was that Iran, using its power, closed the Strait of Hormuz for all international trade, which created a storm of inflation. There was a commotion in all the global markets of the world and its effects were clearly visible in every country. The United States President Trump invited all countries of the world, especially China, Russia, and NATO countries, to come forward and open the Strait of Hormuz and help the United States restore international trade. Trump give ultimatum for reopening the Strait of Hormuz but Iran denied. On 1st March Trump said Iran is looking for a

deal but Ali Larejani denied. The United States and Israel entered the war with a very clear goal, believing that it would last no more than a week because Iran did not have the strength to fight them. But the retaliatory attacks and counterattacks given by Iran in return proved that Iran is also a country with a strong fighting force and this created many problems in the region, due to which the US and Israel were very anxious and eager to turn this war into a peace agreement and then conclude a peace agreement to control this situation. Because this war had created a wave of inflation all over the world, due to which people in America and Israel were protesting against this move by the American government and the Israeli government, it was very important to stop this war.

Map shows the Strait of Hormuz along with Iran and other Gulf Countries boundaries

Initially US wants “Unconditional Surrender” by 6 points for settlement. On 23rd March 2026 Trump said we are doing “very good and productive negotiations” with Iran. Trump further said he is negotiation with high officials from IRGC but denied and said no negotiations found. In all this situation, diplomacy finally got a chance to play its role, and after the efforts of various countries, the path towards negotiations and a ceasefire was paved, and the Islamic Republic of Pakistan come forward for diplomacy, presented the American fifteen points to Iran for the first time. Pakistan had strong diplomatic ties

with the world countries particularly with Islamic brotherhood country Iran but not with Israel. Pakistan also did not recognized Israel as an independent state but for peace settlement Pakistan come forward for diplomacy. US threaten to Iran, destroy power plants and oil wells if Iran will not surrender and will not open Strait of Hormuz. These mixed events, i.e. diplomacy and war, were happening at the same time, which made it difficult to assess the situation. However, Pakistan, while maintaining the high standards of diplomacy, was successful in creating a conducive environment for

negotiations, and finally the negotiations began. Iran gives proposal of 5 points for ceasefire but US denied.

Pakistani Prime Minister, Shahbaz Sharif

Field Marshal, CDF Pak Army General Asim Munir

Qatar denied to be the mediator but on 30th of March 2026 Iranian foreign ministry stated that they are negotiating with US with the mediation of Pakistan. Trump again threaten and asked to

reopen the Strait of Hormuz but IRGC denied it separately. Finally, after 45 days of war conditional ceasefire for 2 weeks become possible.

Speaker of Parliament of Iran Bagher Ghalibaf

US Vice President JD Vance

Both Iran and US agreed for negotiations and decided Pakistan’s capital Islamabad for it. 11th and 12th of April 2026 decided for table talks in Islamabad, Purpose of ceasefire was to stop escalation in war and it was mandatory for negotiations. Negotiations named “Islamabad talks” all organized by Pakistan’s government and the team for mediation was consist on four members their names are Prime Minister Shahbaz Sharif, CDF Pakistan Army General Asim Munir,

Ishaq Dar Foreign Minister of Pakistan and Muhammad Asim Malik National Security advisor for Pakistan. JD Vance vice president was leading the delegation of US with three companions and Muhammad Bagher Galibaf was the leading the delegation of Iran with three companions for negotiations. No body from Israel was the part of negotiations even Pakistan prohibited Israelis journalists because Pakistan foreign policy is clear on Israel and Palestine issue

When Bagherr Ghalibaf, Speaker Iran Parliament, arrived Pakistan for Islamabad talks, he brought with him the bags of 168 martyred children of Minab School, so that he could prove that America committed war crime and martyred innocent children’s. Arab media named this flight “Minab 168”

During Islamabad talks Iran gives a proposal of 10 points, US-Israel stop attacking on Iran also on Lebanon and Iraq, guaranty for no more aggression, no more war repetitions, nuclear enrichment rights but we will not make the nuclear bomb, US-Israel and others pay for the destruction in Iran during war, unfreeze Iranian assets, stop invasion on Hezbollah etc., allow regional diplomacy, reorganization of Iranian sovereignty on Strait of Hormuz, unfreeze assets and UN security council provides guaranty for all of it. US said Iran will not have the nuclear program and give the enrichment uranium to US. After 21 hours long negotiations JD Vance said in the morning on 12 April 2026, we have not reached the deal but we gave best deal to Iran and told them our red line but Iran not chosen our terms. Abbas Aragchi Iranian Foreign minister posted on social media we were inches away from the agreement but US Vice President JD Vance

suddenly demanding irrationally and backed out that’s why we not reach the final agreement. Negotiations were secret and little information was released but breakdown come on the issue of establishing peace in Lebanon but substantives development were found. Both countries also hinted at further talks, and thus the first round of the talks came to an end. However, this was the first time that negotiations were held to resolve a long-standing conflict, which reflects a very high level of diplomacy on the part of Pakistan, which was the result of the way Pakistan had maintained its relations with Iran, the US and other countries in the past. This was the result of Pakistan's diplomatic effects, that the trust that had been lost in diplomacy between the US and Iran because there was no implementation of agreements for a long time and no adherence to any ceasefire was being observed. Pakistan played an important role in restoring all this lost trust, which completely

paved the way for negotiations and held negotiations in Pakistan. On the other hand, Israel hit 100 bombs in Lebanon in just 10 minutes but after Islamabad talks Israel and Lebanon agreed for the 10 days ceasefire during the negotiations in USA.

Peace was obligatory for US President Trump because Americans was protesting against Trum and on the other hand, war effecting US relations with Russia, China and other countries. Trump said to Netanyahu for ceasefire in Lebanon.

Trump wants to vindicate he is peace maker president and looking for Nobel Peace prize that's why JD Vance said after 1st round of negotiations, Trumps looking for big deal. On 15 April 2026, US blocked all trades of Iran and China will not be able to get one ship but Iran was started using other ports but after that US himself facing implications of Blockade. US faced huge level loss in the War which also was not in favor of US. On these grounds we can say that peace was more mandatory for US and for President Trump.

This picture is taken from Al-Jazeera created by Alia Chughtai on 30 Apr, 2026 which shows the military loss of US in war with Iran.

After just two days, US President Trump said 2nd round of negotiations will also hold in Pakistan. Trump said PM Pakistan Shahbaz Sharif and Favorite Filed Marchal Asim Munir doing good and playing important role. Iran was also agreed for 2nd round of negotiations in Pakistan. On 15 April 2026 Pakistani PM Shahbaz Sharif started three nations tour, Saoudi Arabia, Qatar and Turkey, PM Shahbaz talked about the regional security and peace, biliteral relations of the nations. These visits paved the way for more negotiations to reach the final settlement. Meanwhile, Filed Marchal Asim Munir visited Iran, meet with President Masoud Pezeshkin and

discuss the grounds of negotiations after the 1st round to reach the peace settlement. These visits aim for diplomacy and back door settlements for the finalization of peace negotiations. These visits of Premier and Field Marchel are the first's visit after the Islamabad talks and war respectively. After Filed Marchal Asim Munir visit, Iran completely opens the Strait of Hormuz for trade. US President Trump thanked Pakistan PM Shahbaz Sharif and Filed Machal Asim Munir for efforts and also thanked Iran for opening Strait of Hormoz. Trump further said, the deal with Iran has been final and they will give us the entrainment uranium dust and will not have the

nuclear bomb. Iran dismissed all of Trump's claims as baseless and trying to claim victory, Bagherr Ghalibaf, further said, we will never move our uranium to any other country. Iran closed the Strait of Hormuz again on 18 April 2026 and starting patrolling meanwhile Iran using other ports for trade. Iran President told US is a terrorist state because US invade anywhere in the world any time. US started blockade of Strait of Hormuz and Iran also closed ports, Iranian Supreme Leader Mojtaba Khamenei said that Iran now has the strength to fight more, the strength to fight more vigorously, and it is fully ready to teach the enemy a lesson.

As the first round of negotiations ended and a new wave began, with new contradictory statements from both countries, such contradictions emerged from various figures, including US President Donald Trump and Iranian officials, that it seemed unlikely that this agreement would ever reach its conclusion because both countries did not seem ready for it. The leadership of both countries and their statements showed a continued stalemate in all efforts, in which we clearly saw how both countries seemed far from reaching this agreement, but Pakistan, playing its full role in it and looking at all the issues, was busy in efforts to bring it to fruition. A deadlock situation arose on both sides, due to which reaching a complete deal again seemed very difficult.

America's Iran war had a very bad impact on Trump's personality, which not only made a big difference in his popularity but also damaged his Christianity, which is one of his agendas, because Israel is a Zionist state in which there are no facilities not only for Muslims but also for Christians, which is why many Americans condemned the fact that President Trump should not stay in this war any longer. War even not just impacts on Trump's personality also effecting the popularity of Republican Party. War even effecting the bilateral relations of US and Israel. It is just because of violation of international law and genocides in different countries.

US-Israel and Iran war was turned into an international crisis due to blockade after the 1st round of negotiations. Israel attacked on petro

chemical plants in Iran and in confrontation Iran attacked on Saudi Arabs petro chemical plants, which make the situation more complex. Situation become more complex and controversial for negotiations particularly for Pakistan as a diplomatic country due to Pakistan alliances with Saudi Arabia. Initially, the ceasefire was for 2 weeks but on 22nd April last night before ceasefire deadline, US President Trump said, we have extended the ceasefire on Pakistan request till the negotiation's process will end but US forces will continue blockade of Hormuz. Trumps prohibited Israel to attack on Lebanon to maintain the ceasefire. Iran considers it a trick to take time for attack. This shows how of an atmosphere of distrust had been created.

Overall extension in ceasefire was another achievement of Pakistan's diplomatic efforts. Pakistani diplomatic efforts saved the thousands of lives, saved the region from higher level of destruction and recession. Pakistani efforts prevented a new wave of war from erupting again. Pakistan role was very significant and Pakistan played as a mediator effectively to stop escalation. US blockade Strait of Hormuz, Abbas Aragchi foreign minister told US blockade is the violation of ceasefire. Iran has initiated that first the US lifts the blockade of Strait of Hormuz, then we will participate in the second round of Islamabad talks. Imposed sanctions to all those who was providing weapons to Iran. Further US threaten all countries, will impose sanctions if anyone secretly trading with Iran. Both countries US and Iran were alleging each other to broking ceasefire. All was controversial no clear ways for the negotiations. In such circumstances, it was very difficult for diplomatic negotiations to survive during incidents, but Pakistan played its full role in the great and complete diplomacy and made it possible. All of these events show how's the diplomacy was in trouble and failed again because US President Trump has created an atmosphere of distrust. Pakistan efforts were incredible in restoration of diplomacy and creation environment of truth among US and Iran.

On 23rd of April 2026 Iranian President Masood Pezeshkian said, Tehran wants "Dialogue and agreement" but "breach of commitment" are the

main obstacle to genuine negotiations. In actual, Iran wants foolproof guaranties from United Nations, United Security council. No traditional success was found during 1st round of negotiations and an anxiety remains in the minds of the both countries leaderships even the leaders of whole region. Successful Negotiations and peace settlement were obligatory even not just for the entire region and the whole world countries were suffering because of this unrest situation. US President Donald Trump is repeatedly trying to sabotage the Iran deal and is repeatedly openly trying to reach an agreement between the US and Iran. On the other hand, the tension in the Strait of Hormuz and the blockades imposed by both sides have also created an unstable situation, which has made diplomatic negotiations very difficult. However, Pakistan and its diplomatic leadership are still trying to hold a second round as soon as possible and stop the negotiations at a fruitful point and make a complete peace settlement a success.

It was the controversial movement where both side Iran and the US was not trying to make the peaceful treaty successful. Because they are doing

irrational or irrelevant things. In the region, particularly in the Strait of Hormuz, while the closed by the Iranians and the US Navy, and it makes the kind of situation more troubling for the negotiations, Meanwhile Pakistan was ready for the 2nd round of negotiations. Abbas Aragchi the most prominent person from Iran for negotiations, to Pakistan for the meeting with the Prime Minister of Pakistan Shahbaz Sharif and the Field of Marshall Asim Munir. Aragchi discussed the whole region situation and a particularly situation in the Starit of Hormuz. After that, he gone to Oman, and then came back again in Pakistan, and then he gone to Russia to meet the Russian President Vladimir Putin, and he discussed the whole scenario but Aracgchi not discuss Iranian Nuclear program. China, Russia and other many countries appreciating the Pakistan diplomatic role in but situation not going for the permanent solution. 2nd round was expected but not responded for it. Israeli defense minister said we want to finish the Khamenei family. Iranian General Muhammad Raza said if US will start war again then Iran will respond with nuclear missiles and it will be the nuclear war.

Abbas Aragchi, Iranian Foreign Minister and Prominent Negotiator

CONCLUSION

In the whole scenario where we have seen that the untrusty environment from both sides, particularly from the US-Israel side, makes the way of negotiations more controversial. Iranians can't want to rely on the temporary's ceasefire or the temporary settlements for the peace actually. Demands from both sides producing hurdles for the negotiations. But in end, we say that at any cost, diplomacy makes the way forward and makes the situations to come to the ceasefire. And it is a remarkable moment for the whole region and a particular for Iran and US. We have seen that how the diplomacy take place and how the difficult ceasefire in the troubling scenario. But the efforts were successful and more huge destruction was stopped. We can say that world just have one way for the peace that are the diplomatic negotiations and all the conflicts are going are the result of lack of diplomatic relations of the countries. Settlements require peaceful environment which possible when two countries come in contact with the mediation of third country. In this case, how the situation is troubling and how the long historical conflict but table talks makes the situation peaceful. The role of Pakistan, as well as Qatar and other countries that played their respective roles in holding these negotiations cannot be ignored at all because this was a long-term conflict in which the path has now been paved for its resolution and the role of many countries in it cannot be ignored. It's a continues situation in the region which is affecting the whole world but diplomates seeking for great deal.

FUTURE RESEARCH

As we have seen how the general of the Iranian military made a statement that if there is another attack now, this attack will be the beginning of the third world war and in the same way if a long conflict continues, the time is not far when the world will be engulfed in this whole chaos and will face a great disaster. Some questions still remain to be addressed. As Iran wants to make an agreement that requires the participation of Arab countries including Pakistan, will it be able to succeed in this? Will the current situation lead to a fruitful agreement? This temporary cease-fire will

not prove to be a ploy to attack? Will Iran abandon its nuclear program? And if the agreement is reached, what will be the effects on the economy of the whole world, especially on the economic situation of Iran? If no agreement is reached, what will be the US's foreign policy towards Iran and if an agreement is reached, what will be the US's policy? Another important question that arises is whether or not there will be an agreement between the US and Iran. But if an agreement is reached, what will be Israel's foreign policy towards Arab countries, particularly Iran? Will a comprehensive and stable agreement be reached and how will all participating countries comply? These questions are raised only to provide opportunities for further research and to explain the matter further.

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